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Report on Train-the-Trainer programme implementation

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Author name(s)	Vasia Madesi, Nathalie Wuiame, Anne Laure Humbert
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Partners

SUMMARY

This report provides an overview and evaluation of the Train the Trainers programme held under the GenderSAFE project. The training programme integrated methodologies and insights from the [GE Academy](#) and UniSAFE projects, using participatory feminist methodologies to ensure active engagement and experiential learning. The two sessions organised aimed to empower trainers with the skills and knowledge necessary to address gender-based violence in research and academia.

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INTRODUCTION

This deliverable, **D4.1 “Report on Train-the-Trainer programme implementation”** presents the design, execution and evaluation of two Train-the-Trainers (TtT) sessions organised as part of the GenderSAFE project. The objective of these sessions was to build capacity among professionals working in higher education and research institutions to deliver high-quality, participatory training on gender-based violence (GBV) using materials developed under the UniSAFE and GenderSAFE projects. The sessions were designed to not only transfer knowledge, but also to equip participants with practical skills, methodologies and pedagogical standards that foster safe, inclusive and impactful learning environments.

Objectives of the Train-the-Trainer programme

The GenderSAFE Train-the-Trainer programme had the following core objectives:

- To **develop training capacity and expertise** for facilitating sessions that address gender-based violence in research and academia;
- To **familiarise participants with participatory gender training methodologies**, adapted specifically for the topic of gender-based violence;
- To **enable the effective use and adaptation** of the UniSAFE/GenderSAFE training scripts, including associated tools such as case and persona stories, protocols and evaluation templates;
- To **promote the use of feminist pedagogical principles**, with a specific focus on creating safe spaces and adhering to the [GE Academy quality standards](#);
- To prepare participants to **handle challenges such as resistance** and institutional inertia when delivering gender-based violence training.

The deliverable is structured in two main parts, each dedicated to one of the Train-the-Trainer sessions. Both parts include:

- A description of participant recruitment and profiles;
- A detailed account of each training day;
- Reflections and feedback from participants;
- Lessons learned and recommendations.

The report concludes with an analysis of the feedback collected through exit questionnaires.

Recruitment of participants

Participant recruitment followed two different approaches for each session to serve distinct strategic goals.

- **First session (5–6 June 2024):** Participants were selected via direct invitation based on their active involvement in the UniSAFE project, their previous experience as trainers in gender equality programmes (such as GE Academy and GEARING-Roles), and their institutional roles (e.g., ombudspersons, equality officers). The purpose of this selection was to create a strong pilot group composed of professionals who were already familiar with the UniSAFE approach and could provide constructive feedback for the refinement of training materials and methods.

- **Second session (18–20 March 2025):** A broader and more inclusive approach was used. Participants were recruited through an open call circulated among members of the GenderSAFE Community of Practice. The call aimed to reach individuals from widening countries, underrepresented regions and institutions with varying levels of experience in gender-based violence training. This approach not only ensured greater diversity but also enabled the programme to pilot the same materials in a wider range of contexts and institutional cultures.

In both sessions, care was taken to include individuals with a professional mandate or motivation to implement structural change in their institutions. The diversity in geographical representation, institutional roles and familiarity with the topic proved valuable for peer learning and allowed the training team to tailor facilitation styles and content levels accordingly.

Profile of participants

Across the two sessions, there was a total of 25 participants.

The first session brought together 12 participants (8 women and 4 men) representing institutions from Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Spain, the Czech Republic and Austria. The group included university integrity advisors, equality officers, ombudspersons and experienced trainers involved in previous EU-funded projects.

The second session welcomed another 13 participants (12 women and 1 man) from institutions based in Ireland, the UK, Germany, Austria, Slovakia, Spain and Slovenia. This group had diverse professional profiles, including academic staff, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion managers, ombudspersons, equality and consent officers and researchers with experience in institutional gender equality work.

Across both Train-the-Trainer sessions, **four widening countries** were represented: **Portugal, Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Slovenia**. Out of **25 participants**, **eight** came from institutions based in these widening countries, representing **32%** of the total cohort. All participants demonstrated strong motivation to engage with the training content and showed a high level of professional commitment to promoting inclusive and safe academic environments. The diversity of professional backgrounds and national contexts significantly enriched the discussions and collective learning throughout both sessions.

FIRST TRAIN-THE-TRAINERS SESSION

This section summarises the proceedings and outcomes of the first GenderSAFE Train-the-Trainers session conducted online on June 5th and 6th, 2024. The training aimed to equip participants with advanced tools and methodologies for addressing gender-based violence in research and academia. The session was led by Nathalie Wuïame and Vasia Madesi (Yellow Window).

Participants were invited based on their active involvement in [UniSAFE](#) activities, their roles as trainers in [GE Academy](#) and [GEARING-Roles](#) EU-funded projects, and their experience in training. They were recommended by consortium partners and approached via personal invitations. These participants were selected for their potential to act as change agents in their respective areas, considering their background and current professional status.

The twelve (12) participants (8 women / 4 men) came from across Europe (Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Spain, Czech Republic and Austria). This geographical diversity brought a variety of perspectives to the session which was particularly valuable in addressing the challenges of addressing gender-based violence in different cultural and institutional contexts. This group had different professional backgrounds, including university integrity advisors, student ombudspersons, and representatives from (past) gender equality projects such as GE Academy and GEARING-Roles, policy advisors in ministries, university staff responsible for equal treatment and gender policy implementation from diverse academic and research institutions.

The main aim of the train-the-trainers programme was to equip participants with training capacity and expertise to effectively adapt and facilitate sessions on addressing gender-based violence in research and academia. They learnt how to apply gender training methodologies and tools for designing and conducting participatory training, use training scripts and supporting materials from UniSAFE / GenderSAFE, and how to create a safe space for discussion and dialogue in gender-based violence training sessions. Additionally, they learnt about quality standards in gender training, following the Gender Equality Academy principles with a specific focus on gender-based violence.

During the training, the co-trainers from YW facilitated a series of interactive exchanges and discussions designed to enhance the participants' skills in creating inclusive and effective training environments. In what follows, the activities undertaken are outlined, as well as the methodologies employed, the group dynamics observed and the feedback received, concluding with recommendations for future training of trainers activities.

TRAINING CONTENTS AND ACTIVITIES

Preparation required from the participants included participating in an introductory training session held on April 30th, which covered the 7Ps framework for addressing gender-based violence, essential for understanding the foundational concepts of the training. Those unable to attend were provided access to a recording to review the material at their convenience. Additionally, participants were encouraged to familiarise themselves with the UniSAFE toolkit and the UniSAFE capacity-building materials, which were made available online and in PDF formats. These preparatory steps were essential for participants to fully benefit from the training, allowing them to actively engage and contribute to the discussions and activities planned.

Day 1

Introduction

The day started with an optional **MIRO board tutorial** to familiarise participants with the collaborative online tool, enhancing their ability to engage interactively throughout the session. Then, the facilitators introduced the objectives and encouraged participants to share their **expectations** in a roundtable, which revealed a common desire for practical strategies to address gender-based violence and enhance their training skills, focusing on strategies for dealing with resistance in a training setting. An **ice-breaker activity** followed, designed to encourage participants to get acquainted with one another, fostering a conducive learning environment. This activity not only helped break down barriers among participants but also stimulated active engagement, ensuring everyone was comfortable and ready to participate fully in the following training activities.

Short quiz

As the session moved into a presentation of the 7Ps framework, it began with a **short quiz** designed to gauge participants' preliminary understanding and to spark reflective thinking on various forms of gender-based violence and response strategies. The quiz questions ranged from identifying different types of violence - such as physical, psychological, and organisational - to understanding the nuances of mediation in cases of gender-based violence, thus setting a thoughtful tone for the discussion that followed. The facilitators then unpacked each component of the 7Ps, linking them to the scenarios from the quiz. This approach ensured that participants were conceptually equipped and practically prepared to engage with the material in a meaningful and context-specific manner.

Applying participatory techniques: Lotus Blossom and Journey Mapping with a focus on Persona Stories

Participants were introduced to participatory techniques like Lotus Blossom and Journey Mapping to deepen their application of the 7Ps framework in addressing gender-based violence. The facilitators, adapting the SUPERA guide of participatory techniques, demonstrated how these techniques could be used to analyse and respond to various gender-based violence scenarios.

Then, each group worked with a selected persona from UniSAFE's collection, depicting individuals facing or witnessing gender-based violence in academia. Using the Lotus Blossom technique, groups explored underlying causes and potential interventions for their assigned personas. This method allowed a structured analysis of the central issue, branching out to examine various influencing factors and responses. One group employed Journey Mapping to trace the persona's experience through institutional responses, from initial reporting to solution. This visualisation helped identify critical intervention points and moments where the persona might have felt unsupported. These activities reinforced the practical use of the 7Ps framework, illustrating how structured and empathetic approaches are essential in effectively addressing complex issues of gender-based violence in academic settings. The group work was followed by discussion and reflection on the use of the participatory techniques.

How to create a safe space and using the GE Academy Quality Standards booklet

The session also discussed creating a safe training environment and adhering to the gender training standards as outlined in the GE Academy Quality Standards booklet¹. This session was to help participants understand the importance of fostering a secure and inclusive atmosphere, which is fundamental when dealing with sensitive topics like gender-based violence. Facilitators outlined practices for establishing safety and respect, such as maintaining confidentiality, ensuring respectful communication, and actively involving all participants. Additionally, they introduced the gender training standards, which serve as a guideline for creating quality gender training that respects diversity and promotes equality. This part of the session emphasised the need for trainers to not only impart knowledge but also model these standards to encourage a holistic and respectful learning environment.

Dividing participants into two groups based on their level of experience with UniSAFE

To enhance the training experience, participants were divided into two groups based on their prior experience with the UniSAFE project. Those already familiar with UniSAFE engaged in advanced discussions about participatory techniques. This allowed experienced trainers to refine their skills and explore new ways to improve their sessions.

On the other hand, those new to the UniSAFE project were introduced to the basic training materials. This group focused on learning the core elements of these resources and discussed how to use them effectively in their training environments. Facilitators helped these participants understand how to apply the guides and capacity-building materials (such as the action plan, protocol, and guide for awareness-raising campaigns) in real scenarios, focusing on adapting and tailoring the content to meet their specific needs.

This approach ensured that all participants, regardless of their initial knowledge of UniSAFE, received training appropriate to their level.

Introduction to UniSAFE/GenderSAFE scripts

Participants were introduced to the UniSAFE/GenderSAFE training scripts. This session was designed to familiarise trainers with structured resources and methods for addressing gender-based violence in academic settings. The facilitators presented a detailed script overview, discussing the objectives, target audiences, and practical applications. This portion of the training provided participants with a toolkit of ready-to-use materials that could be adapted to their specific training contexts.

Hands-on exercise: designing a training session

Finally, participants engaged in a practical exercise where they designed tailored training sessions using UniSAFE resources and participatory techniques. The facilitators provided two scenarios based on the UniSAFE introductory training script²; one scenario corresponded to a training session targeted at participants from Central and Eastern European countries (CEE); the second scenario had to target participants from advanced institutions (for the provided scenarios, see the appendix). The groups started by thoroughly analysing the two provided scenarios to understand the unique contexts and challenges

¹ Cacace, M., d'Andrea, L., & Marta, F. (2022). D3.3 Quality standards Booklet (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6586324>

² Polykarpou, P., Wuiame, N., & Madesi, V. (2023). Setting up and implementing institutional policies to address gender-based violence in academia. Antwerp: Yellow Window.

they presented. This deep dive into context helped participants define their target audience, ensuring the training would meet the specific needs and knowledge levels of different institutional roles.

Each group was assigned one scenario. Building on their scenario, each group crafted a detailed script for their session, choosing engaging formats and activities such as lectures, quizzes, group discussions, and role-playing. The requirement was to integrate at least one participatory technique into their training design, leveraging the UniSAFE toolkit alongside their personal expertise to create dynamic and impactful educational experiences. This hands-on exercise demonstrated how to adapt educational resources to various learning environments, enhancing the participants' ability to design and deliver practical training sessions using UniSAFE/GenderSAFE materials.

To wrap up the first day, a feedback and reflection session was conducted.

Day 2

Introduction

The second day began with a review session where participants reflected on the learnings from Day 1, reinforcing their understanding of the 7Ps framework and the interactive techniques used. The facilitators recapped the previous day's activities, ensuring all participants were aligned and ready to tackle more advanced applications of their skills. Following the ice-breaker, participants shared the outcomes of their group activities from the previous day. This session allowed for reflection on the application of participatory techniques and UniSAFE materials, discussing what worked well and what could be improved. It was an interactive session that encouraged open feedback and collaborative learning.

Hands-on session: mini-training

In this hands-on session, participants had the opportunity to put their skills to the test by conducting mini training sessions. Each group presented a short segment of their training design, implementing the strategies and tools they had developed. This exercise allowed participants to practice their facilitation skills in a supportive environment. After each presentation, constructive feedback was provided by both peers and facilitators, focusing on delivery, engagement techniques, and the effective use of training materials.

Dealing with resistances and other potential challenges

This session addressed how to handle resistances and other common challenges that trainers often face. Facilitators drew on comprehensive resources such as the Festa Handbook on resistance to gender equality in academia³, the works of Mergaert &

³ Saglamer, G., Tan, M., Caglayan, H., Almgren, N., Salminen-Karlsson, M., Baisner, L., Myers, E., Jørgensen, G., Aye, M., Bausch, S., O'Connor, P., O'Hagan, C., Richardson, I., Conci, M., Apostolov, G., & Topuzova, I. (2016). Handbook on resistance to gender equality in academia. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311651308_Handbook_On_Resistance_To_Gender_Equality_In_Academia

Lombardo on gender mainstreaming and resistance to training⁴, and insights from the SUPERA project and Ferguson & Mergaert's guide on resistance to gender equality⁵.

The session emphasised that while specific work on resistance towards gender-based violence implementation and training is limited, understanding resistance in the context of gender mainstreaming is crucial. Resistance should be viewed not as a barrier but as a diagnostic tool to identify and address deeper systemic issues. It is an ordinary and necessary part of the change process.

Participants engaged in discussions to explore different forms of resistance they might encounter. Strategies were discussed on how to navigate and leverage these resistances to improve training implementation. One proposed solution was to use data and arguments to support gender equality initiatives in academia and research, demonstrating the tangible benefits of such efforts. Another suggestion was to seek windows of opportunity to introduce gender-related topics in less confrontational ways, such as framing discussions around broader human rights issues to avoid immediate backlash.

Eva Oliva from ISAS, a member of the GenderSAFE team, shared her experiences and strategies for overcoming resistance based on her work in conducting training using UniSAFE materials in the Czech Republic. Her insights provided practical examples that enriched the discussion and offered valuable lessons for all participants. She highlighted the importance of preparing for expected resistances and building confidence through practice and strategic planning.

Drawing from her work in Czech academic institutions, she stressed that resistance can often be an opportunity marking a critical moment when new conversations begin. She encouraged trainers to view resistance not as a disruption, but as a moment for subversion, discussion, and learning.

One recurrent form of resistance she encountered involved dismissive or mocking comments, particularly around identities such as non-binary or trans people. Eva shared a concrete example where a participant remarked that “people nowadays may say they feel like a cat or a chair” in response to a discussion on gender identity. She recommended responding with empathy but also setting boundaries, offering analogies to help participants understand self-identification in more human and respectful terms. Trainers, she suggested, should not feel obliged to answer every inappropriate remark and must be attentive to their own wellbeing.

She also highlighted the recurring argument that “gender-based violence doesn’t happen here,” and advised reframing such statements through a structural lens, pointing to institutional hierarchies and power imbalances. Her strategy included highlighting the lack of prevalence data as a reason for perceived absence and drawing on the lived reality of students and staff who often remain silent due to fear of repercussions.

Beyond handling resistance, Eva stressed the importance of strategic session design. This includes collecting contextual information about the host institution beforehand such as who

⁴ Lombardo, E., Mergaert, L. (2016). Resistance in Gender Training and Mainstreaming Processes. In: Bustelo, M., Ferguson, L., Forest, M. (eds) *The Politics of Feminist Knowledge Transfer*. Gender and Politics. Palgrave Macmillan, London. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-48685-1_3

⁵ Ferguson, L., & Mergaert, L. (2022). Toolkit: Resistances to structural change in gender equality. SUPERA guide https://www.superaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Resistances-to-Structural-Change-in-Research-and-Innovation_v02.pdf

will attend, what their knowledge level is and whether potential victims or perpetrators may be present. Her methodology includes flexibility, gradual sensitisation and clear framing of session goals. She underlined that it is okay to defer questions, assert boundaries and end sessions if the atmosphere becomes hostile or unsafe.

On creating safe spaces, Eva recommended simple but meaningful actions such as giving content warnings before discussing sensitive material, acknowledging diverse experiences and encouraging inclusive introductions with pronouns when appropriate. She warned against underestimating power dynamics within training sessions and advised trainers to remain aware of academic hierarchies that may inhibit open participation.

Finally, she encouraged trainers to use data strategically, share personal motivations to stay grounded and build alliances to sustain their energy and commitment. Above all, Eva's contribution emphasised that trainers must care for themselves as much as they care for the quality and impact of their training.

Reflections and closing

Participants reflected on how they could apply the competencies gained during the training in their professional roles. This discussion helped them identify specific strategies and contexts where they could implement their new skills, planning for the integration of these methods into their ongoing work to address gender-based violence in academia. Final reflections highlighted the participants' appreciation for the balance between theory and practice, the value of practical tools and techniques discovered, and the importance of preparation and teamwork. Many participants expressed how they looked forward to applying these methods and appreciated the opportunity to share experiences and learn collaboratively.

The session closed with facilitators summarising key take-aways and expressing appreciation for the participants' dedication and engagement. Participants were encouraged to stay connected with each other and continue sharing experiences and resources, fostering a network of support and collaboration.

EXIT QUESTIONNAIRE AND FEEDBACK ANALYSIS

Score	Number of respondents	8	6 F / 2 M									average
	GenderSAFE - Exit Questionnaire: Train the trainers (5-6 June 2024)	4		3		2		1				
		Absolutely / very much	Quite	Rather not	Not at all	No answer						
	Did you learn what you expected to learn during the session?	7	88%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	Point to what extent the session has reached its learning objectives											
	Develop training capacity and gain the expertise to effectively adapt and facilitate training sessions on addressing gender-based violence in research and academia.	7	88%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	Apply gender training methodologies and tools for designing and conducting participatory training.	6	75%	2	25%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,4
	Be able to apply training scripts and supporting materials from UniSAFE.	7	88%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	Create a safe space for discussion and dialogue in a training session on gender-based violence.	6	75%	2	25%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,4
	Adhere to quality standards in gender training using the Gender Equality Academy Principles, with a focus on gender-based violence.	6	75%	2	25%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,4
	How satisfied are you with the trainers?	8	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	10,0
	How satisfied are you with the following aspects of the session?											
	The visual supports	7	88%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	The resources and references provided	7	88%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	The balance between theory and practice	7	88%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	After your participation in the TtT, do you feel:											
	more confident to deliver training on addressing the gender-based violence	4	50%	4	50%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	8,8
	better equipped to deliver training on addressing gender-based violence	6	75%	2	25%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,4
	Overall, how satisfied are you with this session?	7	88%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
		too short		just right		slightly long		too long				Overall average
	How did you find the duration of the training?	0		7		1		0				9,5
	After your participation in the TtT, do you feel:											
	more confident to deliver training on addressing the gender-based violence	4	67%	4	33%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	
	better equipped to deliver training on addressing gender-based violence	6	89%	2	11%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	

Participant feedback highlighted the effectiveness of the interactive exercises and the practical relevance of the scenarios discussed. The use of participatory tools for group activities facilitated a hands-on approach to learning, making the theoretical aspects more tangible. Reflections in the final session underscored the appreciation for the balance between theoretical grounding and practical application, with many noting the empowerment they felt from the new methodologies learned.

Some highlighted feedback for improvements included:

- *"More precise instructions and narrow references for short-timed activities (Persona exercise)."*
- *"To have more time and switch the roles during the exercises."*
- *"Maybe the composition of the groups could have been a bit more balanced, in terms of knowledge and experience (although I guess it is difficult to do!)"*

Some highlighted feedback indicating satisfaction:

- *"Presentation of participatory tools and materials and the exchange with the colleagues. A perfect combination between theory and practice."*
- *"The group work was really valuable and although initial difficulties it worked pretty well. I also liked yesterday's ice breaking exercise a lot."*

The feedback from the exit questionnaire indicates that the training was highly effective in meeting its objectives. Participants felt better equipped with many expressing increased confidence and readiness to apply the new methodologies and tools. The overall average satisfaction score was 9.5 out of 10.

LESSONS LEARNED

Reflecting on the first edition of the GenderSAFE Train the Trainers programme (June 2024) a number of valuable lessons have emerged that will inform the refinement and delivery of future iterations.

One of the most prominent takeaways was the necessity of striking a meaningful balance between theoretical foundations and practical application. Participants consistently expressed appreciation for the way the training sessions moved beyond conceptual frameworks to offer tangible, action-oriented tools and participatory techniques. The integration of exercises such as the Lotus Blossom and Journey Mapping, along with the use of persona-based storytelling, helped to translate abstract principles into lived realities. These methods increased engagement and also enabled participants to visualise how institutional change can be pursued in practice.

Secondly, the importance of allowing sufficient time for discussion, feedback and group reflection was underscored throughout the training. The richness of the exchanges especially when participants shared their institutional contexts, challenges and strategies reinforced the value of peer learning. However, it also became clear that the agenda could benefit from more spaciousness between sessions to allow for deeper exploration of topics, particularly when dealing with emotionally and politically sensitive issues like gender-based violence. Future editions could consider incorporating more time for debriefing and informal exchange to consolidate learning and peer support.

Another important lesson emerged around the topic of resistance. Participants showed a strong interest in learning how to recognise, address and navigate resistance whether it comes from individuals, institutional culture or subtle forms of disengagement. While resistances were addressed conceptually and through the use of the UniSAFE/GE Academy materials, participants indicated that they would benefit from additional case-based learning, role-playing scenarios and examples from practice. This would help prepare them to face difficult questions or challenges with confidence and to respond strategically.

In terms of group dynamics, the training confirmed that diversity among participants across roles, institutional types, geographic regions and professional experience enriched the learning environment. This diversity enabled valuable comparative discussions and encouraged reflection on how local contexts influence both the manifestations of gender-based violence and the potential for institutional change. At the same time, such diversity also highlights the need for differentiated support during training delivery, recognising that not all participants begin from the same level of familiarity or confidence with the content.

Finally, the importance of modelling inclusive facilitation practices throughout the training cannot be overstated. The trainers' approach characterised by openness, encouragement, flexibility and care was repeatedly cited as a factor that made participants feel safe, respected and motivated. Fostering this environment was essential for meaningful participation, especially in sessions where difficult topics such as harassment, trauma and structural inequalities were discussed.

Taken together, these lessons suggest that future editions of the Train the Trainers programme should prioritise participatory, flexible and context-sensitive approaches. More time should be allocated to the application of tools, the handling of resistance and the consolidation of shared learning.

SECOND TRAIN THE TRAINERS SESSION

This section summarises the proceedings and outcomes of the second GenderSAFE Train the Trainers session, conducted online from 18 to 20 March 2025. Organised over three half-days, the training built on the methodology and feedback from the first session, aiming to deepen participants' skills in delivering high-quality training on gender-based violence in research and academia. The session was co-facilitated by Vasia Madesi (Yellow Window) and Anne Laure Humbert (University of Gothenburg).

Participants were recruited through an open call disseminated to the GenderSAFE Community of Practice and selected based on their professional experience in gender equality, familiarity with academic and research settings, and prior engagement in training activities. Special consideration was given to individuals from widening countries, and the final selection ensured a diverse mix of backgrounds and institutional affiliations.

A total of nineteen (19) individuals were accepted, of whom thirteen (13) participated in the training. The participants (12 women / 1 man) represented institutions from Ireland, the UK, Germany, Spain, Austria, Italy, Slovakia, Poland, and Slovenia. Their professional profiles included equality officers, ombudspersons, academics, Diversity Equity and Inclusion managers, and project officers working on sexual harassment prevention and institutional gender equality. This broad and complementary mix contributed to a rich and reflective learning environment, fostering exchange across various institutional roles and national contexts.

The overall objective of the training remained the same: to enhance participants' ability to deliver tailored training sessions on gender-based violence in academic settings. Participants were equipped with practical tools and participatory methodologies drawn from the UniSAFE and GenderSAFE projects. They engaged with structured training scripts, learned how to create safe and inclusive spaces for dialogue, and gained confidence in applying feminist pedagogical standards. The second session also introduced several new elements based on lessons learned from the first round allowing more time for practice and reflection, offering deeper exposure to participatory techniques, and addressing resistance more explicitly.

In what follows, the content of each day is presented, along with the methodologies employed, examples of group work and exercises, participant reflections and recommendations for further application of the training approach.

TRAINING CONTENTS AND ACTIVITIES

In preparation for the second Train the Trainers session, participants were asked to engage with several key resources to ensure a shared baseline of knowledge and to foster active engagement throughout the training. Participants were required to watch the introductory training video on the 7Ps framework (available in English and other languages on the GenderSAFE YouTube channel) and familiarise themselves with the UniSAFE toolkit, including the core capacity-building materials. These resources offered foundational knowledge on gender-based violence in academia and equipped participants with practical tools, including action plan guidance, protocol development, and strategies for awareness-raising campaigns.

Day 1

Introduction and expectations

The training started with an optional MIRO board tutorial for those unfamiliar with the platform, enhancing participants' ability to collaborate effectively in the interactive sessions ahead. The co-trainers opened the day with a welcome and introduction to the training objectives, setting a collaborative tone. A round of introductions was facilitated through an ice-breaker in pairs, where participants identified commonalities; an activity aimed at fostering connection and trust. Participants then shared their expectations and reflected on their confidence and challenges in delivering training on gender-based violence using a Mentimeter quiz.

Exploring the UniSAFE 7P framework and tools

The facilitators introduced the UniSAFE 7P framework through a short interactive quiz and accompanying video. Participants then engaged with the toolkit materials, including resources on protocols, inspiring practices and the awareness-raising guide. Each tool was discussed in relation to its practical application in institutional contexts. Participants reflected on how these materials could be integrated into their own training efforts, focusing on adaptability and local relevance.

Gamified quiz: “The 7P Champion Ladder”

To reinforce participants' understanding of the 7P framework in a dynamic and engaging way, Day 1 included a gamified quiz titled “*The 7P Champion Ladder*” hosted on Mentimeter. Participants competed either individually or in small teams, climbing a metaphorical ladder of knowledge from *Prevalence Pro* to the ultimate level of *7P Champion*. Each correct answer advanced the players to the next level, while incorrect responses offered learning opportunities through short debriefs by the facilitators.

The quiz combined elements of fun and friendly competition with critical reflection, featuring real-life scenarios and questions across varying levels of difficulty. Topics covered included the purpose of collecting prevalence data, distinguishing between prevention and provision strategies, identifying institutional failures in protection, and understanding the importance of partnerships in strengthening policy.

This structured approach helped participants consolidate theoretical knowledge, sharpen their understanding of the distinctions between each “P”, and prepare for the practical applications that followed. It also served as a useful barometer for facilitators to identify which areas participants were most or least confident in.

To complement the quiz, a Zoom poll was conducted at the beginning of the session to assess participants' self-perceived confidence across key areas of training facilitation. Participants were asked to anonymously respond to the following statements:

- I feel confident about delivering a training on gender-based violence in academia.
- I feel confident in facilitating difficult discussions about gender-based violence in academic and research settings.
- I feel equipped to handle resistance and scepticism from participants.

- I adapt my training style and content to different institutional and cultural contexts effectively.
- I believe trainings that address gender-based violence can lead to meaningful structural change.

The poll was followed by an open-ended question: *“What do you find most difficult in developing and delivering trainings on gender-based violence in academia?”*

Responses were later reflected upon in plenary, guiding the tone of the session and allowing facilitators to tailor their focus to the group’s collective needs. This mixture of quantitative and qualitative engagement techniques set the stage for a participatory and reflective training experience.

Using participatory techniques: linking stories to methods and training delivery

In the second half of the morning, participants explored how participatory techniques can be effectively applied in training sessions that address gender-based violence. Drawing on the *Co-creation and participatory approaches towards addressing gender-based violence in research and academia* guide developed under the GenderSAFE project (Denis, Madesi, & Wuiame, 2024), facilitators introduced a range of participatory tools and methodologies specifically designed for co-creation in academic contexts. The session began with a brief poll on participants’ prior experience with such methods. This allowed facilitators to gauge familiarity and tailor guidance accordingly.

Following a presentation of the available materials; namely the persona and case stories included in the UniSAFE toolkit; participants were divided into two groups. Each group was given a persona: a fictional character representing an individual affected by gender-based violence in an academic or research setting. Each persona was accompanied by contextual information on their institutional background and lived experience.

Within each group, one participant was selected to act as the **trainer or facilitator**, while the remaining group members engaged as active **participants**. Using either the **Journey Map** or the **Lotus Blossom** method, participants explored:

- Institutional gaps in supporting the persona
- Potential solutions for identified barriers
- Strategic interventions at different points of the institutional response

The **Lotus Blossom technique** helped participants break down the root causes and ripple effects of institutional inaction or complicity, while the **Journey Mapping exercise** visualised how support (or lack thereof) shaped the experience of survivors or witnesses over time.

Groups then "trained" each other in plenary by simulating the delivery of the exercises. This added a layer of peer learning and enabled participants to observe facilitation styles, group dynamics, and engagement techniques in action.

Importantly, participants were encouraged not to seek ‘correct answers’, but to reflect on how these participatory tools made them feel, and how they might be received by different

audiences in a training setting. These reflections highlighted the power of persona- and story-based learning in building empathy and shifting institutional cultures.

The session reinforced the added value of using structured participatory methodologies to support institutional change processes, particularly when dealing with complex and sensitive topics such as gender-based violence. By grounding the exercises in real-life inspired cases and adapting feminist pedagogical principles, participants gained first-hand experience of how to use participatory tools in a way that is ethical, inclusive, and impactful.

Wrap-up

The day concluded with a reflection session, where participants shared key takeaways and noted areas they found challenging. The facilitators previewed the next day's focus, reinforcing the importance of safety, structure and participatory principles in gender training.

Day 2

Introduction and warm-up

Day 2 began with a welcome message and an overview of the day's structure, building on the key takeaways from the first session. The facilitators aimed to establish continuity, linking the previous discussions on participatory methods and the 7P framework with the more practice-oriented content of the day. A light ice-breaker invited participants to share something surprising about themselves such as a hidden talent or an unusual hobby. This short activity not only maintained the warm, collegial tone of the training but also helped reinforce interpersonal connections among participants.

Creating a safe space and applying gender training standards

The first session of the morning focused on the concept of psychological safety in training settings and the application of the GE Academy quality standards. Facilitators began by presenting the **GE Academy training standards** and introduced the **UniSAFE guide on creating a safe space**, underlining their relevance when working with sensitive and potentially triggering topics such as gender-based violence.

Participants explored the difference between predefined safe space rules versus collectively created group agreements. This prompted a reflective discussion: should trainers provide a standard set of rules, or should they co-develop these with participants to encourage ownership and trust? Several participants shared examples from their own institutions, highlighting practices that either supported or undermined the creation of inclusive and respectful environments.

The session continued with an introduction to the PERFCKTSI principles (Participatory, Empowerment, Reflexivity, etc.), helping participants ground their training practice in feminist pedagogical values. These principles were linked directly to the UniSAFE and GenderSAFE scripts and materials, which were then presented in detail.

Using the UniSAFE / GenderSAFE scripts

The next session focused on the structured training materials developed through the UniSAFE and GenderSAFE projects. Using a shared screen and PowerPoint presentation, the facilitators walked participants through:

- The **objectives and structure** of the one-day training script;
- Examples of activities included in the script;
- The **table of definitions** for different forms of gender-based violence;
- Templates such as the exit questionnaire and feedback form;
- Additional formats available (e.g. condensed sessions or advanced workshops).

The facilitators explained the rationale behind each component and how they can be adapted to different institutional or national contexts. Participants asked clarifying questions around audience targeting, session duration, and managing discussions on difficult or controversial topics. This practical overview helped demystify the use of the training scripts and highlighted the flexibility and breadth of the materials provided.

Hands-on design of a training session

Following the break, the session transitioned into a **practical group exercise**. Participants were split into three working groups and assigned one of two scenarios reflecting different institutional training contexts. Each group was provided with a scenario document, accessible via shared links, including:

- An introductory session aimed at raising awareness (country-specific context to be selected by the participants)
- A session on developing institutional action plans

Using the UniSAFE materials and at least one participatory technique, each group crafted a training plan, including format, activities, and expected outcomes. The exercise encouraged teams to consider pedagogical flow, timing, and participant engagement.

Group presentations and peer reflections

Each group then returned to plenary and presented a short summary of their training design. Presentations focused particularly on the pedagogical choices made, the integration of participatory techniques, and the anticipated challenges in delivery. Participants reflected on the diversity of training approaches and the ways in which the same toolkit could be used flexibly across contexts.

Facilitators provided feedback, highlighting strengths such as contextual awareness, creative adaptation of materials, and attention to inclusivity. They also encouraged participants to consider next steps in their own institutions for applying these design exercises in real-life training settings.

Wrap-up and take-aways

The day concluded with a collective reflection on the learning journey so far. Participants were invited to share their personal highlights, remaining questions, and thoughts on how they would use the training tools in their professional contexts. Common takeaways included:

- A renewed appreciation for feminist pedagogical frameworks;
- Increased confidence in adapting training scripts to different audiences;
- Practical ideas for integrating participatory methods;
- Awareness of the importance of co-creating safe spaces with learners.

The facilitators closed the day by offering a brief overview of the third and final session, which would focus on live delivery (mini trainings), managing resistance and planning for implementation in participants' contexts.

Day 3

Introduction and warm-up

The final day of the training opened with a warm welcome and an overview of the agenda. The facilitators set the tone for a reflective and practice-oriented session, which would allow participants to consolidate their learning and gain hands-on experience in delivering training.

As a light and personal ice-breaker, participants were invited to share a short story about a **significant object** within reach such as something on their desk or in their surroundings. This small but meaningful exercise created a relaxed and human-centred atmosphere, gently encouraging presence and attentiveness before transitioning into the practical sessions.

Mini training presentations and peer feedback

The first core activity of the day involved **mini training presentations**, during which participants had the opportunity to put theory into practice. After a short preparatory moment in breakout groups (20 minutes), two selected participants presented a **10-minute training segment** they had co-developed, with the remaining group acting as the training audience.

Each presentation was followed by structured feedback:

- **Facilitators** offered reflections on content delivery, flow, clarity of messages, and alignment with participatory and feminist pedagogical principles.
- **Peers** shared supportive comments on what was effective and what could be refined.

This session provided valuable insight into facilitation styles, allowed space for experimentation, and normalised constructive critique. Participants appreciated the opportunity to present in a safe environment and to experience group dynamics from the perspective of both trainer and trainee.

Group reflection: Trainer take-aways

Immediately after the mini-presentations, the group engaged in a **guided reflection** on their development as trainers:

- What did we do well?
- What would we want to do even better?
- What surprised us?

This reflective pause helped surface shared challenges such as managing time, balancing participation with structure, and responding to unexpected comments and also highlighted key moments of empowerment and learning.

Dealing with resistance and other potential challenges

The second session on Day 3 focused on a central challenge in the delivery of training on gender-based violence: **resistances**. The goal of the session was to equip participants with both an analytical understanding of resistances and concrete strategies to address them, using insights from academic literature, practice-based tools, and co-creation methods.

The facilitators began by framing resistances as not just an obstacle, but also as a **diagnostic tool** a sign that the training is touching on underlying power dynamics and established norms. Quoting Gandhi's line "*First they ignore you, then they ridicule you, then they resist you, then you win...*", the trainers encouraged participants to view resistance as an inherent part of any transformative process.

Participants were introduced to the **typologies of resistance** as developed in the SUPERA project and by scholars such as Ferguson and Mergaert:

- **How:** Active (e.g. hostile comments, belittling remarks, sexist humour) vs. Passive (e.g. silence, withdrawal, performative agreement).
- **Who:** Individuals, groups, or institutional mechanisms.
- **Why:** Based on David Rock's **SCARF model**, which explains that resistance may be triggered by perceived threats to Status, Certainty, Autonomy, Relatedness, or Fairness.

Concrete examples were given to illustrate how these forms of resistance manifest in academic training settings such as questioning the legitimacy of gender-based violence data, disengagement when discussing privilege or subtle undermining of the trainer's authority.

Collaborative scenario-based resistance exercise

To ground the theoretical discussion in practical facilitation work, participants engaged in a **MIRO-based scenario analysis** focused on common forms of resistance encountered in training sessions on gender-based violence in academia.

The board featured 20 real-life-inspired statements, such as:

- "Gender-based violence doesn't happen in our university."
- "Women should just take more precautions to avoid gender-based violence."
- "Gender-based violence is only a problem in certain cultures, not here."

For each scenario, a suggested **evidence-based response** was pre-populated. For instance:

"Research consistently shows that gender-based violence occurs in all universities, regardless of location or prestige. Underreporting and institutional silence can make it seem invisible, but student and staff experiences tell a different story."

Participants were then asked to **analyse these answers individually**, using sticky notes to identify the **core argument or resistance pattern** underlying the statement (e.g. denial, false equivalency, whataboutism, cultural relativism); reflect on the **strengths of the provided response**; suggest **further improvements** to enhance clarity, empathy or persuasion.

This method allowed participants to **interact with complex dynamics of resistance** without the pressure of live role-play or group debates. The exercise was also an opportunity to **model digital facilitation** using tools like MIRO, demonstrating how trainers can structure critical discussions visually and accessibly.

Participants appreciated the layered structure of the task, as well as the how to develop learning tasks and exercises using AI (here using ChatGPT) based on tech-assisted pedagogical principles. The facilitators discussed how they had used AI to generate the initial examples, encouraging critical thinking about the use of digital tools in feminist training design. This added an important **meta-level of reflection** on tech-assisted pedagogies and how trainers might creatively, yet responsibly, integrate such resources.

The training concluded with a collective reflection exercise, designed to help participants consolidate their learning and begin envisioning how to apply their new knowledge and tools in their own professional contexts. Using a MIRO board, participants responded to a set of reflective prompts, focusing on immediate takeaways, future integration, and anticipated challenges. The exercise was both introspective and practical, offering space for individual thought as well as a sense of shared direction among peers.

When asked to share *one idea they could apply immediately*, several participants emphasised their intent to begin designing training scripts using the UniSAFE and GenderSAFE resources. For many, the script was not only a structural tool, but also a means of creating a feeling of safety for participants. Others highlighted the importance of introducing the GE Academy training standards in their institutions, thereby fostering consistency and quality in training delivery. The idea of “learning in action” resonated strongly. An approach that encourages trainers to move forward even without perfect conditions, embracing trial, reflection and iteration.

In terms of longer-term integration, participants expressed clear intentions to embed feminist pedagogical principles such as those encapsulated in the PERFCKTSI framework into their broader training strategies. Many highlighted the role of safe space creation, kindness and care in shaping effective facilitation, especially when addressing resistance or emotionally charged topics. Several participants shared that they would prioritise maintaining a conscious, inclusive tone in language and content, while also committing to self-care as a vital part of sustaining themselves as trainers in this work.

Another key theme was the creative use of digital tools. Participants discussed plans to make more regular use of platforms like Miro, Mentimeter to promote engagement and interactivity in both online and in-person trainings. The use of ChatGPT in the co-design of training elements particularly the exercise of dealing with resistances was seen not only as a useful example, but also as an invitation to experiment with new technologies while remaining critical of their limitations.

Many of the MIRO board entries captured the energy and inspiration of the group through affirming messages. Quotes such as “We all have a superpower” “Don’t be discouraged, keep spirits up” and “The plan is nothing, but planning is everything” reflected the supportive spirit that had developed throughout the three-day training. These comments highlighted the dual importance of peer learning and emotional grounding in delivering effective gender-based violence training.

The training closed with a short overview of the resources available through the GenderSAFE and UniSAFE projects, including training scripts, case and persona stories, participatory technique guides and evaluation tools. Participants were invited to complete the exit questionnaire and were warmly encouraged to continue exchanging practices and insights.

The final words from the facilitators focused on appreciation for the openness, thoughtfulness and commitment shown by participants and for the shared belief in building safer, more inclusive academic environments. It was clear that the participants were leaving not only with tools, but with a renewed sense of purpose and community.

EXIT QUESTIONNAIRE AND FEEDBACK ANALYSIS

Score	Number of respondents	9	9 W / 0 M									average
	Exit Questionnaire: Train the trainers 2025 edition	4		3		2		1				
		Absolutely / very much		Quite		Rather not		Not at all		No answer		
	Did you learn what you expected to learn during the session?	8	89%	1	11%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	Point to what extent the session has reached its learning objectives											
	Develop training capacity and gain the expertise to effectively adapt and facilitate training sessions on addressing gender-based violence in research	7	78%	2	22%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,4
	Apply gender training methodologies and tools for designing and conducting participatory training.	8	89%	1	11%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	Be able to apply training scripts and supporting materials from UniSAFE.	9	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	10,0
	Create a safe space for discussion and dialogue in a training session on gender-based violence.	9	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	10,0
	Identify typical barriers and obstacles in implementing structural changes to address gender-based violence.	8	89%	1	11%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,7
	Equip future training participants to develop counter arguments and use strategic framing for advocating structural change to address gender-based	7	78%	2	22%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,4
	Adhere to quality standards in gender training using the Gender Equality Academy Principles, with a focus on gender-based violence.	7	78%	2	22%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	9,4
	How satisfied are you with the following aspects of the session?											
	Visual supports	9	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	
	The resources and references provided	9	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	10,0
	The balance between theory and practice	9	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	10,0
	How satisfied are you with the trainers?	9	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	10,0
	Overall, how satisfied are you with this session?	9	100%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	10,0
		too short		just right		slightly long		too long				Overall
	How did you find the duration of the training?	0	0%	7	78%	2	22%	0	0%	0	0%	9,8
	After your participation in the TtT, do you feel:											
	more confident to deliver training on addressing the gender-based violence	6	67%	3	33%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	
	better equipped to deliver training on addressing gender-based violence	8	89%	1	11%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	

The overall satisfaction with the second Train the Trainers session was high, with an average rating of 9.8 out of 10. All participants reported that they learned what they had expected to and felt either absolutely or very much confident in applying the learning objectives. Notably, all nine participants felt completely confident in using UniSAFE training scripts and in creating a safe learning space, two of the programme's core goals.

The participants found the training particularly valuable for strengthening their facilitation capacities, understanding resistance dynamics and applying participatory methodologies.

LESSONS LEARNED

The second edition of the GenderSAFE Train the Trainers programme, held in March 2025, built upon the foundations laid in the first round and introduced a number of new elements in response to the earlier feedback. This iteration offered several important insights that will further inform the development of future training activities.

A key lesson from this session was the strong value of extended time and a multi-day format. Structuring the training across three half-days provided participants with space to absorb complex material, revisit concepts and return each day with fresh reflections and new questions. This pacing allowed for deeper engagement, particularly with topics such as resistance and safe space creation, which benefit from both emotional and cognitive processing over time. The improved rhythm of the agenda was well received and supported more sustained interaction among participants.

The incorporation of gamified elements, notably the 7Ps Champion Ladder quiz, emerged as a particularly effective strategy for reinforcing content while keeping energy levels high. The playful and competitive format allowed participants to revisit essential elements of the 7P framework in an engaging way, demonstrating that learning on serious topics can still be dynamic and accessible. Combined with other tools such as Zoom polls and MIRO boards, this approach confirmed the relevance of integrating interactive, digital methods into feminist training, especially in online settings.

Another important lesson related to the centrality of peer learning and practice-based exchange. The mini-training presentations and participatory exercises (e.g. persona stories linked to Lotus Blossom and Journey Mapping⁶) were consistently highlighted as high impact moments. These activities enabled participants to try out facilitation techniques in a safe environment and allowed them to learn from each other's approaches, language use and ways of managing group dynamics. Participants particularly valued the opportunity to observe each other in action and to receive feedback both from peers and from facilitators.

⁶ The participatory exercises used during the training sessions, including Lotus Blossom, Journey Mapping were adapted from the following guide: Denis, A., Madesi, V., & Wuame, N. (2024). Co-creation and participatory approaches towards addressing gender-based violence in research and academia. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13986398>. This guide offers practical methodologies specifically tailored for addressing gender-based violence in research and academia through co-creation and participatory approaches. It is publicly available and can support institutions seeking to implement similar Train-the-Trainer activities or gender-based violence trainings more broadly.

The session on resistance confirmed the continued need for practical strategies, strategic framing and emotional preparedness. The revised version of this session, which included typologies of resistance, real-life examples and a MIRO collaborative exercise, created space for participants to explore this complex issue without pressure. The discussions around the use of AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT-generated prompts) in developing exercises encouraged critical discussion on the ethics and creativity of using digital support in feminist pedagogy.

A significant lesson from this session was the benefit of offering structured reflection prompts throughout the training. From early-stage polls and confidence check-ins to the final “one idea you can apply tomorrow” wrap-up board, the use of short, focused questions encouraged thoughtful participation without requiring extensive time or verbal input from everyone. This also created an inclusive environment where different personalities and communication styles could be accommodated.

Lastly, the session confirmed the importance of nurturing trainer resilience and wellbeing. By addressing the training content and the facilitation mindset and emotional care, the programme helped normalise the reality that trainers will sometimes encounter discomfort, backlash or fatigue. Discussions on setting personal boundaries, acknowledging vulnerability and seeking support contributed to a healthier vision of what sustainable training practice looks like.

Overall, the second session validated the strengths of the GenderSAFE training approach, particularly its grounding in participatory, feminist and trauma-aware principles, while also reinforcing the need for flexibility, creativity and self-reflection in its delivery. Future iterations will benefit from retaining the core structure and pedagogical values, while continuing to innovate in terms of digital tools, peer-led learning and strategies for navigating resistance with care and confidence.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of the two Train-the-Trainers sessions under the GenderSAFE project marked a significant step forward in strengthening institutional capacities to address gender-based violence in research and academia. Both sessions successfully equipped participants with the necessary tools, methodologies and confidence to deliver high-quality, context-sensitive training within their own organisations and networks.

The progressive structure of the Train the Trainer programme grounded in feminist pedagogical principles and enriched by the integration of the UniSAFE toolkit ensured a balance between theoretical rigour and practical application. Across both editions, participants consistently emphasised the value of participatory methods, experiential learning, and the supportive peer environment created throughout the sessions. The updated structure of the second session, organised over three half-days, allowed for deeper reflection, increased practice and a more robust engagement with complex topics such as resistances and institutional change.

Participant feedback has demonstrated not only a high level of satisfaction but also a strong commitment to applying the learning outcomes in their respective contexts. In both sessions, participants left with concrete tools training scripts, participatory techniques, frameworks for addressing resistance and, importantly, a sense of being part of a wider community. The inclusion of participants from Horizon Europe Widening countries further reinforced the project's commitment to equitable capacity-building and inclusive excellence across the European Research Area.

Looking ahead, the materials and experiences developed through the GenderSAFE TtT programme provide a solid foundation for scaling and adapting this model. Future editions may benefit from even more structured peer-to-peer exchange, follow-up mentoring or community-based reflection spaces. Continued investment in feminist facilitation, safe space creation and strategic engagement with resistance will remain essential components of effective training on gender-based violence in academic settings.

Ultimately, the two Train-the-Trainers sessions have contributed to the broader aim of GenderSAFE: to foster a zero-tolerance culture towards gender-based violence in higher education and research, through knowledge, dialogue and action.

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